

Conveyor Belt Speed Control Efficiency Using the Energy Management Methodology

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Abstract— The article presents an algorithm for optimal regulation of the step speed using the energy management methodology. Methods of reducing the cost of transport costs for conveyor systems are considered. The perspectives of using the energy management methodology as a tool to reduce the cost of energy are shown. Comparative analysis of energy management tariffs has been carried out. The problem of synthesizing stepwise speed regulation is formulated taking into account the tariffs for energy management. The criterion of quality for an estimate of the effectiveness of the transition to the TOU-tariff, differential links and restrictions on control is written. The Hamilton function for the transport system was determined, on the basis of which the synthesis of an algorithm for step regulation of the conveyor belt speed was performed. To construct differential relations an analytical PDE – model of the conveyor section was used, taking into account the transport delay of the material. The efficiency of the transition was assessed and qualitative comparative analysis of TOU-tariffs was carried out based on the speed regulation algorithm. It is shown that for the effective use of the energy management methodology, a combined control system for the flow parameters of the transport conveyor is required.

Keywords — distributed transport system, TOU-tariff, transport delay, the uneven distribution of material.

INTRODUCTION

The use of energy management methodology is one of the ways to reduce unit cost on material transporting in the mining industry. Despite the fact that conveyor transport is the most economical type of material transportation, the cost of material transportation is more than 20% of the total cost of material extraction [1] with the recommended standard factor of loading the conveyor section with material equal to 0.7 [2]. With a decrease in the coefficient of loading the conveyor section with the material, the cost of transportation costs increases nonlinearly and can become the main component in the cost of extracting material [3, 4]. The high share of transportation costs and, accordingly, energy costs in the cost of extracting material is one of the reasons for applying the energy management methodology [5] to reduce the cost of extracting material.

The essence of the approach based on the energy management methodology lies in the use of a tariff plan, within which the cost of electricity depends on the time of day. This requires the development of such algorithms for controlling the flow parameters of the transport system,

which will make it possible to transfer the main energy consumption to periods with a low cost of electricity while limiting energy consumption during peak periods with a high cost of electricity. Such control of flow parameters can be achieved by regulation the speed of the belt [6, 7, 8], the intensity of the flow of the incoming material [9, 10, 11] to the input of the conveyor section from the accumulator hopper, or in a combined way.

To effectively control the consumption of electricity, a sufficient number of tariffs are proposed, among which the tariff with a fixed price during the day (FPT) should be distinguished; tariff with a differentiated price of electricity, which depends on the time of day (TOU) [12]; tariffs in which the price for electricity consumption is determined in real-time (RTT) [13, 14]. The analysis of the tariff structure for Great Britain, Ukraine and South Africa is presented in papers [15, 16, 17]. The overwhelming majority of works devoted to the design of systems for controlling the belt speed and the value of the flow rate from the accumulating bunker were carried out for the case of the FPT tariff, which assumes a fixed price of electricity. The effect of using TOU-tariff for an 8-km conveyor is considered in [18]. Indeed, it is reasonable to assume that the transition from FPT-tariff to TOU-tariff will provide additional cost savings for material transportation.

CONCLUSION

The article discusses the possibility of applying the energy management methodology with step regulation of the belt speed. To analyze the efficiency of FPT–TOU transition, Eskom–TOU tariffs were considered: Nightsave Eskom–TOU periods; high demand season–TOU periods; low demand season–TOU periods. The analysis of the values of the coefficients RC shows that the efficiency of the FPT–TOU transition is higher for transport systems with the highest amplitude of fluctuations of the incoming material flow. The values of the coefficients in many of the cases are in the range $0.95 \leq RC \leq 1.05$. To synthesize an algorithm for multistage belt speed control software has been developed that takes into account the transport delay when moving material along the transportation route and the initial distribution of the material. Since the minimum belt speed is determined by the size of the incoming material flow $\gamma_1(\tau)$, using only the optimal speed control system does not allow effective use of energy management

methodology to reduce the cost of material transportation. A system for controlling the flow parameters of the transport conveyor is required, which allows regulating not only the belt speed but also the amount of material flow from the bunker at the conveyor input. With this regulation, it is possible to stop the conveyor or reduce the speed to the minimum allowable value during periods of high energy costs. This problem determines the prospect of further research on the possibility of applying the energy management methodology in order to reduce the cost of transporting material in conveyor systems.

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